

Traditional Computer Vision in the Deep Learning Era

Objectives and Main Topics: The ability to extract information from images is a cornerstone in the development of intelligent robotic solutions. Over the past 50 years, we have witnessed a shift from traditional geometric computer vision to deep learning-based approaches. Recently, this transition has accelerated rapidly towards AI-based methods, raising the question of whether there is still room in industry and research for non-data-driven approaches.

This workshop aims to bring together experts from both traditional computer vision and deep learning fields to discuss this question. Specifically, deep learning and traditional computer vision experts will be invited to present cutting-edge AI-based solutions and applications, as well as to highlight how traditional computer vision can still make a significant impact in specific domains. The goal is to foster a discussion and determine the role, if any, that traditional computer vision still plays in the era of deep learning.

Keywords: Deep Learning for perception – Traditional Computer Vision – Applications of Computer Vision – Perception for Robotics

Workshop Organizers: **Gabriele Costante** (Department of Engineering – Università degli studi di Perugia – email: gabriele.costante@unipg.it), **Matteo Matteucci** (Department of Information, Electronics and Bioengineering – Politecnico di Milano – email: matteo.matteucci@polimi.it)

Workshop Format: 4 talks of approximately 15 minutes each. At the end of the talks, a round table will be held to open a discussion on the topics covered by the talks. Therefore, the workshop is expected to last up to 90 minutes.

Preferred Date: **Morning/Afternoon of October 26 or 27 2024** (due to the availability of the speakers/organizers)

Expected Audience: We expect **30-50 participants**, including academic researchers, industry, practitioners, policy makers and students.

Possible Products and Repercussions: Presentations and videos may be shared upon permission of the speakers. The workshop is also expected to provide insightful discussion regarding traditional and deep learning-based computer vision in industry and academia. In addition, the objective of the workshop is to make a census on the people interested in topics related to the technical working group on Artificial Vision and Contactless Perception.

List of Speakers (with affiliation and talk information):

Federica Arrigoni - *"I am a traditional Computer Vision Believer"*

Affiliation: Department of Electronics, Information and Bioengineering, Politecnico di Milano, Italy

Vito Renò - *"I use Deep Learning when and if needed"*

Affiliation: Institute of Intelligent Industrial Technologies and Systems for Advanced Manufacturing – National Research Council of Italy, Italy

Primo Zingaretti - *"I am moving to the dark side of Deep Learning"*

Affiliation: Department of Information Engineering, Università Politecnica delle Marche, Italy

Massimiliano Mancini - *"Traditional Computer Vision: who?"*

Affiliation: Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science, University of Trento, Italy